

INVESTIGATION OF THE SOLVENT UPTAKE IN ADHESIVELY BONDED CFRP JOINTS USING NON-DESTRUCTIVE DIELECTRIC AND DESTRUCTIVE MECHANICAL TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Adhesive bonding of both primary and secondary structures within the aerospace and related industries is becoming ever more popular, necessitating further research into adhesive ageing processes and non-destructive evaluation (NDE). By developing and applying high frequency dielectric techniques, this study has successfully investigated the deterioration of carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) bonded structures, caused by water and solvent ingress, at accelerated ageing temperatures. The dielectric measurements were conducted in both frequency and time domain using the Hewlett Packard HP 8753 A network analyser through the frequency range 300 kHz to 3 GHz. A Zwick tensile testing machine was used for the mechanical shear and cleavage tests.

CFRP joints were aged in aviation fluids (including water), at 65°C. To complement the NDE technique, ultrasonic methods and destructive mechanical testing were used, with the latter allowing for correlation between dielectric behaviour and structural integrity. The adhesive used to bond the joints was AF-163, a modified epoxy, which is widely applied to load bearing aerospace joints, requiring high strength and excellent environmental durability.

Dielectric methods monitored solvent uptake into the CFRP joints, with better results achieved for those fluids exhibiting higher dielectric constants. Such ingress however, did not adversely affect the adherend/adhesive interface, although uptake in the CFRP was realized,

which influenced the shear data. Overall however, there were good correlations between mechanical strength and dielectric properties measured.

The study has clearly demonstrated the usefulness of high frequency dielectric analysis as a NDE tool, with particular relevance to defect detection and location, as well as solvent uptake, correlated to the joint's structural integrity depletion.

Keywords: high frequency dielectric spectroscopy, non-destructive testing, adhesively bonded joints, CFRP and solvent uptake.

INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins are widely used as matrices for structural composite materials and adhesives. They are extensively employed in aerospace applications. Despite the many advantages associated with the use of advanced structural materials doubts still remain as to the ability of adhesively bonded joints to withstand the full range of environmental conditions experienced during service; in particular exposure to warm/moist environments. Ingress of moisture into adhesively bonded structures is known to degrade the bond strength of joints or the mechanical properties of CFRP composites [1]. Degradation of bonded structures occurs when the adhesive absorbs significant amounts of moisture. Once the water penetrates the bondline, the adhesive properties can be altered in a reversible manner by plasticisation or in an irreversible manner by hydrolysis or crack and craze formation.

The potential of the dielectric technique to monitor the ageing of adhesively bonded joints has been discussed previously [2-6]. The current paper attempts to establish whether a correlation exists between the changes in dielectric permittivity and the mechanical properties of adhesively bonded CFRP structures exposed to a variety of common aviation fluids, at elevated temperatures. In doing so the use of dielectric spectroscopy as a new NDE method for the assessment of composite materials will be displayed.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

In this study CFRP adhesively bonded joints were constructed. The composite adherends were manufactured using Fibredux 914C-TS(6K)-5-34% pre-preg, supplied by Hexcel, Duxford, UK. This pre-preg material contained unidirectional, surface treated, high tensile carbon fibres (Torayca 300B) which were pre-impregnated with a modified epoxy matrix (914), resin content 34 %, so that when cured, each lamina had an approximate thickness of 0.125 mm. From this the optimum number of layers was determined to be eleven, giving an approximate thickness of 1.37 mm. The cure cycle of heating to 175 °C at 20 °C min⁻¹ with 7 bar pressure, and being held at 175 °C for 1 hour was used to cure the CFRP adherends. The adhesive used was a structural epoxy system, supplied by 3M, and designated Scotch-Weld Brand AF 163-2M. The joint structures were autoclave cured at a temperature of 125⁰C under a pressure of 2 bars for 1 hour.

The CFRP joints were aged in solvents commonly encountered by aircraft, at a temperature of 65⁰C. These included; de-ionised water, simulated ocean water (ASTM: D 1141-90), AVTUR F-34 (military aviation fuel), OM18 DEF STAN 91-48/1 (hydraulic fluid), ethylene glycol (anti-icing agent), butanone and dichloromethane (paint strippers). The dichloromethane was studied at room temperature due to flash point hazards.

As well as dielectric monitoring, the CFRP joints were also monitored gravimetrically. In addition to the non-destructive evaluation, mechanical tests were conducted (on joints aged under identical conditions) at specified intervals, to determine the strengths of the ageing joints and to establish whether or not a correlation existed. These tests were conducted in both Mode I and Mode II, to determine the cleavage and shear properties respectively, of the bonds.

Dielectric measurements were performed at high frequencies only, 300 kHz to 3 GHz, using a Hewlett Packard 8753 A network analyser. A Zwick tensile testing machine was used to apply a crosshead separation rate of 1.27 mm/minute for shear testing and 3.00 mm/min for cleavage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following section details and discusses the results of the ageing of epoxy bonded CFRP specimens.

Dielectric, gravimetric and dimensional analysis

Figure 1 Plots of the average change in (a) permittivity at 3 MHz, (b) mass, (c) thickness and (d) width, against the square root of exposure time for joints exposed to various environments

In Figure 1 the dielectric, weight, thickness and width change profiles are presented for CFRP adhesively bonded joints in various environments. Considering the dichloromethane system, from the dielectric analysis, it was found that although solvent uptake was present and detectable, such characteristics were masked by the high dissolution experienced by both adhesive and matrix. However, by simply assessing the mass uptake, it appeared that rapid diffusion was encountered, followed by equilibrium after around 14 days. Similar results were also indicated from the dimensional measurements, although after the initial 14 days, a more gentle increase was encountered. The equilibrium observed in the mass plot can be attributed to the rate of solvent ingress equaling the rate of dissolution. By looking at the butanone aged joints, a similar response to that of the dichloromethane was observed. Clearly in this case, the rate of dissolution was greater than the mass of butanone diffusing into the bonded specimen. From visual observations, these adherends were the worst affected by matrix dissolution, particularly by 105 days, and so it was speculated that this was the cause for the above variations.

Considering the water aged joints, steady Fickian-like diffusion was reported for the water ingress into the CFRP joints, and this too was concluded from the mass and dimensional results shown in Figure 1. Further, as all four of the plots detailed increases, it was concluded that as well as the adhesive absorbing a significant amount, so did the CFRP adherends. Similar results were also found for the ocean water aged specimens although to a slightly lesser degree.

Considering next the CFRP joints aged in hydraulic fluid (OM-18), although the permittivity results indicated a slight reduction, the mass and dimensional measurements detailed no significant variation. Similarly, the mass variations for the aviation fuel (AVTUR F-34) showed a small decrease in mass, with the thickness seen to increase very slightly along with a decrease in width. The tentative conclusion was therefore that the adhesive was swelling due to solvent uptake, but also a component of the adhesive was being dissolved out.

For ethylene glycol, it can be seen that the mass decreased slightly, the width increased and plateaued after 45 days and that the thickness only started to increase after 177 (13.3²) days. Such results therefore indicated uptake in the adherend, with matching dissolution to balance the mass. Also, a gradual increase in permittivity was recorded which increased more sharply around the time that thickness variations were measured. Reasoning for such effects was therefore related to the adhesive eventually swelling, allowing for easier solvent diffusion. However further ageing and analysis would be required to fully explain this result.

As may be expected, the control specimens exposed to the ambient laboratory conditions altered very little with respect to mass and thickness, although a slight reduction in width was experienced, which was used to explain the fractional increase in permittivity measured.

Time domain analysis

Figure 2 (a) details the time domain data for butanone in the form of waterfall plots. The change in transit time for the reflection waves follows the previously discussed trends in permittivity with ageing. The reflection trace maintained reasonable definition, with no additional reflection pulses, inferring intimate interfacial contact remained and no significant voiding had occurred. However the significant drop in permittivity observed suggests a decrease in the mechanical properties of the joints. A similar result was observed for dichloromethane aged joints.

Figure 2 (b) for water details the weakening of the first reflected signal, along with its migration to higher transit times as the permittivity correspondingly increased. As for the subsequent reflection signals, these were reduced until only the second reflection was present. Surprisingly however, this second reflection signal gained in amplitude even as the first was diminishing, a phenomenon not yet understood. There were no indications of defects forming within the joint, although this was expected, due to the positive work of adhesion resulting in

thermodynamic stability, even in the moist environment. Again similar results were recorded for sea water aged joints.

Figure 2 Time domain reflectometry, shown as waterfall plots for joints aged under (a) butanone and (b) water

No significant alterations to the time domain traces were observed for joints aged in hydraulic fluid, aviation fuel, ethylene glycol of the control samples and so are not shown in this paper.

Mechanical testing

Figure 3 (a) shows the evolution of the shear strength with ageing time. Clearly the butanone was the most depletive solvent, followed by the dichloromethane environment, although it must be remembered that the latter was only ever aged at room temperature. Other notable effects were the slight increase in strength towards the end of the study for the water-aged joints, and the even greater increase associated with the ocean water specimens. Increases in strength were also observed towards the end for ethylene glycol and aviation fuel, but only the former could be detected or predicted by the non-destructive evaluation techniques. The reasoning associated with these gains, as discussed above, was as a result of the adherends becoming more flexible and extendable, allowing the fracture loads to be transferred to the tougher adhesive, which was also absorbing solvent and plasticising.

Figure 3 also shows a plot of the interlaminar fracture toughness data, for each of the solvents, against ageing time. From this, it was clear that at the crack tip (b), both the dichloromethane and butanone aged equally and rapidly. However for the bulk G_{IC} , Figure 3 (c), the dichloromethane was not nearly as aggressive. Also, it can be seen that the ethylene glycol diffused and attacked the cleavage strength in a linear manner, both at the crack tip and in the bulk, with the former being affected more. As for the water and ocean water, it may be said

that by accounting for errors, these two systems were essentially equally affected. It was also noticed that the hydraulic fluid and aviation fuel were least affected.

Figure 3 Detailing the mechanical shear strength (a) and the calculated G_{Ic} values at (b) crack initiation and (c) 45 mm into the bond, for cleavage CFRP joints, aged in dichloromethane at room temperature and butanone, water, ocean water, hydraulic fluid, aviation fuel and ethylene glycol at 65°C.

Correlation between mechanical strength and change in permittivity

Figure 4 (a)-(d) illustrate the shear failure strength against changes in permittivity, thus allowing for easier interpretation of any trends that exist. Considering the dichloromethane aged system Figure 4 (a) the positive/negative permittivity trend restricted a true correlation. Despite this, due to the test intervals implemented, a tentative downward trend was seen, with the shear strength decreasing as the permittivity decreased. Further, upon drying the strength was significantly recovered, although the permittivity was not, dismissing the simple use of the dielectric permittivity technique for blindly predicting the lap shear strength of this dichloromethane aged/dried joint system. On the other hand, much more promising correlation results for butanone-exposed specimens are shown in Figure 4 (b).

Figure 4 Correlation plots of mechanical shear strength against change in dielectric permittivity for joints aged in (a) dichloromethane (and dried), (b) butanone (and dried), (c) water (and dried), (d) ocean water (and dried)

Here as the ageing time progressed (up to 16 days) and the permittivity increased, so the drop in lap shear strength measured, dropped in a linear fashion, with minimal distribution. Unfortunately, after this period, the change in permittivity with respect to the original data began to decrease, as the strength continued to decrease. Also, by conducting the drying programme after this initial 16 day period, these results too were removed from the linear trend. Despite this, it is expected that if the drying had been conducted during this primary ageing period, the reduction in permittivity measured and the associated gain in strength, may well have remained on the ageing trend line. An extension to this study would have to be carried out to confirm such speculation.

The next system to be addressed is that of water ageing/drying, Figure 4 (c). Again, a general linear trend was tentatively seen, although broad, and could not account for the increase in strength experienced for the 300 days aged samples. The straight-line trend did however recognise the reversible effects of drying (although with a slightly negative permittivity change). Similarly, although with better resolution, the ocean water aged/dried specimens also indicated a correlation between the measured change in permittivity and mechanical lap shear strength. Unfortunately, due to the effects of the test with respect to adherend influence, the joints aged for 300 days were not included in this correlation. However the results of the dried specimens were still acceptable, detailing the return to near original properties.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has shown clearly that the most adverse solvent for CFRP joints are the paint strippers. Even for the dichloromethane at room temperature adverse effects on mechanical properties were evident.

Dielectric monitoring is seen to be a useful NDE tool for determining solvent ingress in joints. Time domain reflectometry showed correlation with trends in permittivity.

Correlation of mechanical properties with dielectric results was attempted. Some tentative trends could be seen. Further work is necessary in this area to obtain definitive results.

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